

Assessment Questions for Open Science Infrastructures

This questionnaire is designed to help evaluate Open Science Infrastructures¹ to make our evaluation as simple as possible. If the requested information is published online, please include the respective link in addition to your answer.

Name of infrastructure:

Link to website:

1. Organisation and Communities	
1.1. Which organization is in charge of your infrastructure?	
1.2. Which community do you consider your main user group?	
1.3. How do you organize quality control of content?	
1.4. What kind of statistics or evidence do you provide to demonstrate added value?	

2. Goals and Finances	
2.1. Please explain the funding model of your infrastructure.	For example: crowdfunding, membership model.
2.2. Please describe your strategy for sustainable long-term financing of your infrastructure.	
2.3. Please provide information regarding the finances of your infrastructure (annual budget/financial report).	
2.4. Briefly describe the organization running your infrastructure. Is it a not-for-profit organisation?	For example, a company, a foundation, an association, a university.

¹ For a definition of Open Science Infrastructures, see UNESCO [Recommendation on Open Science - Legal Affairs](#)

3. Future, Mission & Tech	
3.1. Please explain your strategic and technical development plan for the next 3-5 years.	
3.2. Briefly describe the mission of your infrastructure. In addition, please share your published mission statement.	
3.3. Which licences are supported and used for content hosted or created?	For example, metadata is licensed under CC-BY.
3.4. Are you generating metadata? If yes, are they in a machine-readable format?	For example, do they adhere to the FAIR Principles?
3.5. Which established Community Standards/Persistent Identifiers do you use?	

4. Transparency	
4.1. How are decision processes and governance organized in your infrastructure?	
4.2. Please provide information about the goals and services of your infrastructure.	
4.3. Which user data do you collect and why?	

5. Innovation	
5.1. Which novel/innovative services within the research life cycle does your infrastructure offer?	
5.2. How does your infrastructure support the advancement of Open Science?	